

HISTORY / ESSAY

Same Script, Different State

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The Kamal Maula mosque complex, photographed in 1912. Hindu groups in Dhar claim that the Kamal Maula mosque is an eleventh century structure called the Bhojshala, a school run by the medieval emperor Bhoja, and that it was the site of a temple to the deity Sarasvati—also referred to as Vagdevi. VERNON & CO./ ROYAL GEOGRAPHICAL SOCIETY / GETTY IMAGES

IN MID SEPTEMBER 2023, hardly two months before the Madhya Pradesh elections, the police arrested four persons for attempting to place an idol of Sarasvati within the premises of the Kamal Maula Masjid, in the town of Dhar. The persons arrested were associated with the Akhil Bharat Hindu Mahasabha, a Hindu nationalist party connected to the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh. The Hindu Mahasabha later claimed that an idol of Sarasvati had spontaneously manifested itself inside the shrine.

The events were an eerie recall of how, in 1949, a supposed manifestation of an idol at the site of the Babri Masjid—also engineered by members of the Hindu Mahasabha—had launched a decades-long political and social dispute. Hindu groups in Dhar claim that the Kamal Maula mosque is, in fact, an eleventh-century structure

called the Bhojshala, a school run by the mediaeval emperor Bhoja, and that it was the site of a temple to the deity Sarasvati—also referred to as Vagdevi. Outside the disputed mosques at Ayodhya, Varanasi and Mathura, in Uttar Pradesh, Hindutva organisations have turned their focus on the Kamal Maula Masjid and the Baba Budangiri shrine in Karnataka, seeking political mobilisation in the name of religious beliefs.

Over the past three decades, especially when a Congress government was in charge in Madhya Pradesh from 1998 to 2003, Dhar saw numerous attempts by Hindu groups to lay claim to the site, leading to a series of standoffs between demonstrators and the police. Adhering to guidelines issued by the Archeological Survey of India, in April 2003, the state government allowed Hindus to pray at the site on Tuesdays, and Muslims to offer namaz at the mosque on Fridays. After the mobilisation of the Congress years, tensions over the shrine had been, for the most part, contained by the Bharatiya Janata Party government led by Shivraj Singh Chouhan, which preferred to maintain the status quo during its two decades in power.

The idea of the Kamal Maula mosque as the Bhojshala is a myth conceived not with an intention to uncover the work of a great king, but by the desire to harvest political gains by propagating lies.

The news of the supposed manifestation in September was reported in the local media, but, nationally, it got lost in the din of the election campaign. It did not, however, escape the attention of the right-wing news website *OpIndia*, which remains a good place to glean the spin that Hindutva outfits give to current events. “According to reports, a video went viral on social media on the night of 9 September in which it was claimed that an idol of the goddess has ‘appeared’ in the 11th-

century monument. The same night another message with a similar assertion went viral on WhatsApp as well,” *OpIndia* reported. “It was taken from the Bhojshala premises at around 4 in the morning and stored in an undisclosed location after the clip gained traction on the internet ... Superintendent of Police Inderjit Bakalwar characterized it as a conspiracy by mischievous individuals and added that some people put the Saraswati idol there, after severing the wire installed for the security of the premises.”

While reporting on the election campaign in the state, we were able to track down Shiv Kumar Bhargava, a Hindu Mahasabha activist who was arrested for placing the idol at the masjid complex. Bhargava told us that the goddess had appeared to him in a dream and revealed that she had manifested herself in the complex.

Bhargava was attending a Hindu Mahasabha meeting in Harda, Madhya Pradesh, at the time. He told his colleagues what he had seen and travelled with them to Dhar, located over two hundred kilometres away, to see the goddess. “She had appeared inside the courtyard. We picked the idol up, placed it near the sanctum sanctorum and came back,” Bhargava said. “The police and administration reached there, and they removed the idol. Later, we came to know that the ASI said there was no idol. We went to Dhar again and told them we had seen the idol, and that we had done *darshan*. They refused to listen to us and we were arrested.”

🔗 (<https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20187>)

Hindus carrying out a procession in honour of Sarasvati, in Dhar, in February 2003. The year saw a massive communal campaign by Hindutva outfits to demand access to the Kamal Maula Masjid complex. The sustained pressure led the ASI and the government to slowly modify the rights of access to the shrine in favour of Hindus, in complete defiance of the actual history of the site. AFP / GETTY IMAGES

We asked why the goddess only appeared in the dreams of Hindu Mahasabha cadre. He responded, “It is true that the same thing happened in Ayodhya, but then you have to be prepared and ready for the appearance of the goddess.”

The case of the Kamal Maula Masjid complex is evidence of how Hindutva groups construct contentious issues for political ends, keeping these simmering till it becomes useful to bring them to a boil. Over a period of time, these groups have managed to sustain a narrative of dispossession around shrines where history is ambiguous enough to allow space for differing interpretation of events. But the case of the Kamal Maula Masjid complex goes a step further, where

even the cause for the dispute has been constructed out of nothing—a concoction with no basis in either history or myth.

IN A 2012 PIECE in the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, titled “Dhar, Bhoj, and Sarasvati: from Indology to Political Mythology and Back,” Michael Willis, a curator at the British Museum, wrote what amounts to the definitive history of how Hindutva organisations have created the idea of the Bhojshala. The article appeared in a volume of the *JRAS* that was dedicated to mediaeval India and the Paramara dynasty, of which the semi-legendary figure of Raja Bhoja is the best-known representative.

According to Willis, the first mention of the structure in colonial records occurs in John Malcolm’s *Report on the Province of Malwa*, published in 1822, where it is described as “a ruined mosque.” An examination of the written records from the time reveals no mentions of the Bhojshala. “The silence ... on this point,” Willis concludes, “shows that there were no living traditions about the Bhojśālā in the middle decades of the nineteenth century.”

The next significant person in this history is Alois Anton Fuhrer, an ASI employee and German Indologist, who while writing of the mosque in 1893 noted, “On two of the columns supporting the central dome of the masjid are inscribed a couple of grammatical sutras, which show that they were probably part of a scholastic building.” This is the first mention of a school in the context of the structure. In 1898, the historian and civil servant Vincent Smith investigated Fuhrer’s work. Smith uncovered, in Willis’s words, “a breath-taking degree of bad scholarship and bad archaeological practice.” Fuhrer was eventually forced to resign from the ASI.

Willis then traces back the term Bhojshala, used by the Hindu Right for the complex, to a 1903 report, *Summary of the Dramatic Inscription found at the Bhoja Shala (Kamal Maula Mosque), Dhar, C. I., in November 1903* by the superintendent of state education, KK Lele.

The basic conundrum for Lele was that if the mosque at Kamal al-Din was going to be explained away as a re-used Hindu building, then some sort of Sanskrit basis had to be found for 'Bhoja's school', the designation 'Rāja Bhoja kā Madrassa' being too manifestly Urdu to serve his purpose. Lele addressed the problem by inventing the term 'Bhojśālā'. While this was a clever bit of Sanskritisation, it had no basis in common parlance or the architectural types known from śilpa-texts. A *dharmśālā* was and is a well-known place of refuge for pilgrims, and there are various functional buildings called śāla, such as those used by washer men (*dhobīśālā*). But there is no such thing as a Sanskrit śālā (that would be *vidyālaya*, *vidyāpīṭha* or *jñānapīṭha*) and no śāla named after a king.

The first mention of Bhoja's school was the work of a man who was dismissed from service because of bad scholarship. The first mention of the term Bhojshala itself is a neologism that could not have possibly been used in Bhoja's times. Subsequently, the *Western States (Malwa) Gazetteer* of 1908 described the buildings of Dhar and mentioned "Bhoja's school," even as the author, CE Luard, notes that the name "Raja Bhoja's School" was "a misnomer."

↗ (<https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20189>)

A statue of the Jain goddess Ambika, recovered from the ruins of an old city palace in Dhar, in 1875. The statue is currently at the British Museum. Hindu groups claim that the statue depicts the Hindu goddess Sarasvati, and was installed at the Bhojshala, a school run by the medieval emperor Bhoja, at the site of the Kamal Maula Masjid complex. Scholars have disproved this claim—the record only shows the existence of a Jain temple in Dhar that was possibly visited by Bhoja, and the recovery of a Jain statue of Ambika from the town. WIKIMEDIA COMMONS

As Willis put it, the only remaining piece of the Hindutva puzzle is the purported connection to the goddess Sarasvati. It is no coincidence, Willis noted, that the term “Bhojshala” sprung up at a time shortly after the publication of an English translation by Charles Henry Tawney of the *Prabandha-cintamani*, a collection of legends and semi-historical biographies written in 1304 by the Jain scholar Merutunga, who based these on earlier written records. The text has several references to visits by Bhoja to the temple of Sarasvati at Dhar, Willis noted. “Merutunga calls the temple the *Sarasvatīkaṇ ṭhābharaṇa* or *Necklace of Sarasvatī*.” He adds that the fourteenth century text mentions a story, in which Dhanapala, a Jain scholar and author, showed Bhoja “some eulogistic tablets in the Sarasvatī temple engraved

with his poem to the first Jina”—a verse that could only appear in a monument that was sacred to Jains. This clearly suggests that the temple in question was a Jain structure.

This fact is essential to understanding the question of a statue that today lies at the British Museum and that Hindutva organisations want returned to India. In 1924, Indian scholars, including the director general of the ASI at the time, claimed that an idol at the British Museum that was recovered from Dhar was that of Sarasvati. The idol of the goddess, they claimed, was once present in the supposed Bhojshala—conflating both invention and legend, the Bhojshala in the Hindutva imagination became both a temple and school.

Willis rubbishes this claim as well. Historical records showed that, in 1875, the idol was recovered not from the masjid complex but from the debris of the old city palace, which was being rebuilt at the time. While the inscription on the British Museum sculpture is damaged, it does mention Bhoja and Vagdevi, another name for Sarasvati. Subsequent study of the idol further clarified matters. Willis noted that scholars re-examined the inscription and published their findings in 1981, and found “that the inscription records the making of a sculpture of Ambikā after the creation of three Jinas and Vāgdevī.” Ambika is a reference to the Jain goddess. “In other words, although Vāgdevī is indeed mentioned, the inscription’s main purpose is to record an image of Ambikā , i.e., the sculpture on which the record is incised.” He noted that various iconographic details in the sculpture further confirmed that the statue is of Ambika, and not Sarasvati.

The only conclusion that emerges here is this: the record only shows the existence of a Jain temple in Dhar that was possibly visited by Bhoja, and the recovery of a Jain statue of Ambika from the town. There is no reliable historical evidence to connect the statue to the temple or the temple to the masjid complex, and no record of a school of any sort. Evidently, the idea of the Kamal Maula mosque as the Bhojshala is a myth conceived not with an intention to uncover the work of a great king, but with the desire to harvest political gains by propagating lies.

It would be safe to say the debunking of the claims by Hindutva organisations done here is based on material they themselves have asked people to read.

The actual history of the masjid complex is more straightforward and is best understood when compared against the claims made by the Hindutva organisations themselves. There can be no better source for this than the RSS's own publicity department, the Vishwa Samvad Kendra. The Bhopal website for the VSK begins by claiming what has already put to rest above: that the Bhojshala was a Sanskrit education centre built by Bhoja, which housed a temple of Sarasvati, with an idol that now lies outside India, in a museum in Britain.

It goes on to claim that fourteen hundred prominent intellectuals, religious savants and poets have spent time at the Bhojshala, including figures such as the poets Kalidasa and Banabhatta. The absurdity of this is evident from the fact that both these figures preceded Bhoja by several centuries.

The VSK states that Kamal Maulana came to Dhar in 1239 and began conducting conversions to Islam. This is how, the VSK claims, he laid the ground for the mediaeval emperor Alauddin Khilji to invade Malwa. In this narrative, the destruction of the Bhojshala began during Kamal Maulana's time and ended with the 1404 invasion of Dilawar Khan, a ruler connected to the Delhi Sultanate. Khan allegedly destroyed the Suryamartand Mandir and built a mosque in a part of the Bhojshala complex—purportedly the Kamal Maula mosque. During Khilji's invasion, the VSK claims, *vanvasis*—forest dwellers, the term the Sangh prefers to use instead of *Adivasis*—gave their life to defend the Bhojshala. It also notes that twelve hundred people were given the choice between the Quran and “the sword,” and chose death.

None of this has any basis in fact. The ridiculousness of this claim is made evident from an inscription dated 1392–93. Next to the mosque complex is a small structure that houses the tomb of Kamal Maulana, and next to that is a graveyard. The inscription was dug up here. It mentions that the mosques of Dhar had fallen into disrepair and that they were renewed by Dilawar Khan. The inscription dates to a year after Dilawar Khan was appointed the governor of Dhar. He went on to become the ruler of Malwa, a decade later. He did build a new mosque, but it was located close to fort walls, at a considerable distance from the Kamal Maula mosque complex. The inscription confirms that by the time of Khan's appointment, the Kamal Maula mosque had already fallen into disuse and was supplanted by the main mosque, which had nothing to do with the structure the VKS terms the Bhojshala.

The RSS take on the Bhojshala is an absurdity, but it is repeated as fact by the many propaganda outlets that serve to amplify such myths. Virtually the same version of events can be found in *OpIndia* reports in both Hindi and English. Another *OpIndia* article on the subject goes a step further, making the completely erroneous claim that “excavation was done in Bhojshala in 1875 and the magnificent idol of the goddess Saraswati was discovered. The British took it to Britain and now it is kept in a museum in London.”

The English-language *OpIndia* article that regurgitates the VKS version also mentions the killing of 1,200 people and provides a link to its Hindi story. The Hindi story links this claim to the website of the Hindu Janajagruti Samiti—a Hindutva outfit that aims to establish a Hindu Rashtra—which is actually a dead link. However, there is a separate HJS webpage that provides much of this same material, without sourcing it. Ironically, the further reading on the HJM page redirects to exactly the same Willis article that has been cited here. It would then be safe to say the debunking of the claims by Hindutva organisations done here is based on material they themselves have asked people to read.

(<https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20191>)

Shiv Kumar Bhargava, a Hindu Mahasabha activist who was arrested in September 2023, for placing an idol of Sarasvati in the Kamal Maula Masjid complex.

The question of how the mosque was built takes us to the uniqueness of the structure of the early mosques built in the Indian subcontinent. Here, it is worth quoting Willis's description of the various components of the Kamal Maula mosque in full.

The variety of pillars used in the building, and the number of inscribed tablets still visible in the floor with yet others displayed along the walls, show that the materials for this building were collected from a number of old sites over a wide area. The approach to the construction of the mosque deliberately mimics what was done at the Qutb in Delhi. Both buildings do not simply use temple material because nothing else was available or because the use of temple pillars was a triumphant display of Islamic supremacy. Rather, the reuse of old temple parts

represented a comprehensive appropriation of the resources of the past—both architectural and cultural—and their radical reconfiguration into a new kind of sacred space unknown in India before the appearance of Islam. Just as individuals could choose to become Muslim and find a place in the new Islamic dispensation, so too pillars, beams and slabs could be converted and find an appropriate role the new architecture [sic].

THE SHRILL CAMPAIGN by Hindutva outfits to reclaim the mosque in the name of the Bhojshala ebbs and flows depending upon the political needs of the Hindutva project, and has done so for decades. The current status is that the ASI allows Muslims to offer prayers every Friday, and Hindus—despite the lack of reliable evidence of their claim to the site—are allowed to offer puja on Tuesdays and on the festival of Basant Panchami. This inevitably leads to huge law-and-order issues, and an excuse for Hindutva mobilisation, each time Basant Panchami falls on a Friday.

The rights of access to the shrine have slowly, but continuously, been modified in favour of the Hindus. This has been the result of sustained pressure through communal mobilisation by the Sangh Parivar in two phases—first in the aftermath of the Babri Masjid demolition, and then in the run-up to the 2003 assembly election when a Congress government still ruled the state.

In these years, Basant Panchami celebrations in the town of Dhar were used by the Sangh Parivar to conduct its rallying campaigns, and saw several visits by hardline Hindutva figures, including Pravin Togadia, a leader of the militant outfit Vishva Hindu Parishad.

One of the writers of this piece, Hartosh Singh Bal, was present in Dhar during the 2003 mobilisation and reported on it for the *Indian Express*. On that year's Basant Panchami, which fell on 6 February, over twenty thousand people assembled by the Sangh Parivar arrived in town. Through a front organisation, termed the Hindu Jagran Manch, the Sangh had organised a *rath yatra* traversing the district over ten

days and subsidiary yatras reaching out to every village. Most devotees, after waiting in a long queue, offered prayers at the disputed shrine, which was under heavy protection of security forces, before heading to a *dharam sangam*, a religious gathering addressed by Togadia, more than a kilometre away. “Mandirs have been broken and turned in to masjids here,” Togadia told the crowd. “In Dhar, the worship of Sarasvati is not allowed, is this Hindustan or Arabistan?” He later addressed a press conference, where he said, “If the restriction on worship by Hindus is not relaxed, I will turn Dhar into another Ayodhya.”

A little over ten days later, on 18 February, the HJM attempted to storm the site amid the heavy police deployment. Digvijaya Singh, the chief minister at the time, had already made it clear to the administration that the protesters must not be allowed to enter the site under any pretext. After a police lathi charge, Hindu activists began stone-pelting and carrying out acts of arson across the town.

Bhargava revealed that, much like the incident at the Babri Masjid, the manifestation of the Vagdevi idol at the Kamal Maula masjid was a pre-planned act.

The tension at the site continued for months, leading up to the assembly elections in Madhya Pradesh and three other states. On 18 November, Narendra Modi, then the chief minister of Gujarat, arrived to address a rally in the town.

This carried a specific import. The Malwa region of Madhya Pradesh, where Dhar is located, adjoins Gujarat, a state that, just a year earlier, had witnessed large-scale mob violence against Muslims in the wake of the Godhra incident. Modi’s reputation as a hardline Hindu leader was built in the aftermath of the violence.

Seeking to replicate its political success in Madhya Pradesh, the BJP had made Madhu Srivastav, a Gujarati legislator who was the main accused in the Best Bakery case in the Gujarat violence—where over a dozen people, primarily Muslims, were killed—the in-charge of poll management at Dhar. After visiting the complex and conducting a rally at Dhar, Modi held a press conference in Indore on the same day. (This was still a time when Modi was forced to address questions at press conferences.)

Asked about the message the party wanted to project by giving people like Shrivastav such a responsibility in the charged atmosphere of Dhar, Modi lost his cool. “What do you mean ‘like Madhu Shrivastav?’” he said. “He is an elected MLA. If the Congress is so afraid of Madhu Shrivastav, they should have the guts to field Zaheera as their star campaigner.” He was referring to Zaheera Sheikh, an eyewitness of the Best Bakery incident, whose family members were among the victims. “If they believe in social harmony,” Modi added, “they should take her around all the four states.” He then got up and walked off, in much the same manner he would do when the journalist Karan Thapar confronted him with questions about the 2002 violence, a few years later.

<https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20194>

Vishva Hindu Parishad leader Pravin Togadia delivering a speech in Dhar, in February 2003. "Mandirs have been broken and turned into masjids here," Togadia told the crowd. "In Dhar, the worship of Sarasvati is not allowed, is this Hindustan or Arabistan?" Togadia later said at a press conference, "If the restriction on worship by Hindus is not relaxed, I will turn Dhar into another Ayodhya." AFP / GETTY IMAGES

The damage to history and facts had already been done by the time the BJP was elected to power in the state, at the end of 2003. Earlier that year, the ASI, succumbing to pressure from the Sangh and seeking to obey the mandate of the BJP government at the centre, had altered the rights of access to the shrine in favour of the Hindus, in complete defiance of the actual history of the site.

A *Frontline* article from May 2003 listed out the history of the rights to worship at the monument:

... in 1904, the complex was declared a protected monument under the Marathas and the British. It was in 1935 that for the first time the name Bhojshala officially attached itself to Kamal Maula when the civic administration placed a board outside the complex calling it Bhojshala-Kamal Maula mosque ... In 1952, tensions between the two communities surfaced when Hindus planned to celebrate Bhoj Diwas at the structure. The sanction to hold the function was given. This prompted Muslims to celebrate an urs in November 1953. By 1995, while Muslims were allowed to offer Friday prayers, Hindus congregate at the monument on Basant Panchami day.

The ASI's stance prior to 2003 can be seen in a document written just a few years earlier. In 1998, during the tenure of a BJP-led coalition at the centre, the ASI had submitted a detailed written reply in response to a writ in the Madhya Pradesh High Court. The reply, which cautiously limited itself to the historical record and which was quoted in an article in this publication in 2012, is worth recounting in detail.

The ASI noted in it that the state government had, in 1952, classified "the present structure called the Bhojshala and Kamal Maula Mosque" as an archeological monument

and thus it could not be handed over to either the Hindus or Muslims for conversion into a temple or a full fledged mosque and that entry into the said structure can be allowed only for the purpose of Sight Seeing. The Muslim community may continue to offer their Friday Namaz.

Regarding the history of the monument, the ASI stated,

It is most humbly submitted that the factual identity of the present structure is not definitely known, nor can it be ascertained from the study of the structure itself ... There is every possibility that the pillars and ceilings could have been gathered from demolished edifices around Dhar and being material readily available must have been put to use for the construction of the mosque of Kamal Maula.

“The actual location of the original Bhojshala remains a mystery which remains to be solved,” the ASI wrote. “It is reiterated most humbly that the structure, presently under dispute was declared protected as Bhojshala and Kamal Maula Mosque and so it remains protected till today.”

The nature of the statue at the British Museum was also addressed in the ASI’s reply. “It is submitted, that there is indeed an image of the female deity at the British Museum, but to lay claim and identify it as the very same image which was originally placed in the present structure cannot stand,” it said.

In this matter, it is submitted that the famous Indian iconographers have yet to come on to a common platform about the true identify [sic] of the sculpture under question and there exists conflicting opinions apropos this sculpture’s identity, wherein one school of thought considers it as Vagdevi (Saraswati) while the other school thinks it to be that of a Jain Yakshi

Ambika ... It is submitted that even this information provided ... does not state in its absolute clarity that the sculpture was discovered from the present structure, but on the contrary the informations states that the image was discovered from the ruins adjoining the Bhojshala at Dhar.

[🔗 \(https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20196\)](https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20196)

A makeshift temple that houses the idol of Ram Lalla, or infant Ram, installed at the site of the Babri Masjid in Ayodhya, on 8 December, just days after a Hindu mob demolished the mosque. The recent attempt by Hindu Mahasabha activists to install a Sarasvati idol at the Kamal Maula Masjid complex in Madhya Pradesh seems designed to replicate the events of 1949, in Ayodhya, when Mahasabha activists broke into the Babri Masjid to install an idol of Ram. SANJAY SHARMA/HINDUSTAN TIMES

In March 2003, after Hindu groups had conducted a month-long protest at the site, Jagmohan, the union minister for tourism and culture, had written to the state government demanding that the Bhojshala complex be opened for Hindus on Tuesdays. The state allowed this only after receiving written instructions came from the ASI and the union government, on 7 April.

THE EVENTS OF SEPTEMBER 2023 seem designed to replicate what happened on the night of 22 December 1949 at the Babri Masjid. The main protagonist of the night was Abhiram Das, a Brahmin ascetic associated with the Hindu Mahasabha.

Das was handed an idol of Ram Lalla—the infant Ram—by Vrindavan Das, another ascetic. They climbed the wall leading to the inner courtyard, and smuggled themselves into the shrine before midnight, before a change of guard ensured that Abul Barkat, a Muslim, took charge. The details of what occurred that night has been covered in detail in the 2012 book *Ayodhya The Dark Night: The Secret History of Rama's Appearance In Babri Masjid*, co-authored by Dharendra K Jha, one the writers of this piece.

Abhiram's cousin Indushekhar Jha, who was present that night, recounted,

Abhiram Das sat just beneath the central dome of [the] Babri Masjid firmly holding the idol in his hands and we got active. We threw away all the articles [of previous possessors], including their urns, mats as well as clothes and utensils of the muezzin. We then erased many Islamic carvings with the help of a khurpi [a sharp-edged instrument generally used for gardening purposes] from the inner and outer walls of the mosque, and scribbled Sita and Rama in saffron and yellow colours on them.

“Around four in the morning, while it was still pitch dark, the intruders ... lit the lamp and started doing aarti,” *Dark Night* notes. “This must have frightened Abul Barkat who was completely unaware of the developments of the previous night, for it would now be impossible for him to explain as to what he was doing when the vairagis sneaked into the mosque ... This predicament explains not just his inability to do anything that night but also his statement much later.”

A charge sheet was filed on 1 February 1950, based on a first-information report against Abhiram Das and others for intruding into the mosque and defiling it. In it, Barkat was named as one of the nine prosecution witnesses. *Dark Night* cites a translation of Barkat's statement:

He [Abul Barkat] was on duty at the Police Outpost Rama Janma Bhumi on the night between December 22nd and 23rd, 1949. While on duty that night, he saw a flash of Divine Light inside the Babari Masjid. Gradually that light became golden and in that he saw the figure of a very beautiful godlike child of four or five years the like of which he had never before seen in his life. The sight sent him into a trance, and when he recovered his senses he found that the lock on the main gate (of the mosque) was lying broken and a huge crowd of Hindus had entered the building and were performing the aarti of the Idol placed on a Singhasan and reciting: Bhayeprakatkripala Deen Dayala [God has manifested himself].

“What he said in his statement to the magistrate elated the Hindu communalists, but any sane person could easily see through it,” *Dark Night* states. “The fact remains that even those who propagated the miracle theory were later found mocking it.” Bhaskar Das, another ascetic, said, “What else could Abul Barkat say? When such an incident happened while he was on duty, he had no other option but to say what he was told to say in order to save himself.”

The shrill campaign by Hindutva outfits to reclaim the mosque in the name of the Bhojshala ebbs and flows depending upon the political needs of the Hindutva project, and has done so for decades.

Bhargava, the Hindu Mahasabha man arrested for placing the idol at the Kamal Maula masjid complex, is a practicing pandit who told us that he earns well from the families who regularly use his services. We met him at in a small flat in Bhopal, used by members of the Mahasabha as a guesthouse. We were put in touch with Bhargava by

Jaiveer Bharadwaj, the national vice-president of the Hindu Mahasabha, whom we met in Gwalior. Bharadwaj had himself been in trouble with the administration earlier, for attempting to construct a shrine to Mohanlal Karamchand Gandhi's assassin, Nathuram Godse.

Bhargava's version of events is rehearsed, thought out in advance and modeled on the events of the night of 22 December 1949. The goddess appeared to him in a dream, "like she had manifested herself to those who found the idol of Ram Lalla at Ayodhya," he first told us. "If she had not done so there would have been no case, and there would have been no Ram Mandir."

Unsurprisingly, he later revealed that, much like the incident at the Babri Masjid, the manifestation of the Vagdevi idol at the Kamal Maula masjid was a pre-planned act. He told us that he had asked a Bhopal craftsman to prepare the idol eighteen months in advance, and that the craftsman had taken great care to ensure the idol did not look as if it was recently crafted, even going to the extent of finding a piece of stone that had not been cut from a rockface recently.

<https://caravanmagazine.in/history/hindu-mahasabha-ayodhya-madhya-pradesh-kamal-maula-mosque/attachment-20197>

Heavy police forces deployed at the Kamal Maula Masjid complex in February 2016. Hindus are allowed to pray at the site on Tuesdays and on Basant Panchami, and Muslims are allowed to offer namaz on Fridays. In 2006, the festival of Basant Panchami fell on a Friday, and Hindu groups demanded that they be given exclusive

Surprisingly, what separates the two events is not a pretend miracle, or the sequence of historical distortions, or Hindutva mobilisations, but the response of the administration. It serves to illustrate how the eventual destruction of the Babri Masjid was made possible by the collusion of the district administration and a state administration run by a Congress chief minister like Govind Vallabh Pant, who was sympathetic to the aims of the Mahasabha—even though this was happening less than two years after Gandhi’s assassination, when the organisation should have been anathema for those in the Congress. Pant reported directly to Vallabhbhai Patel, the deputy prime minister and home minister who was a Hindu nationalist. This allowed him to act in defiance of Jawaharlal Nehru’s explicit wishes that the administration take action against the placing of the idols.

The events were set in motion by the action, or rather the inaction, of the district magistrate of Faizabad, KKK Nair, whose political affiliations are made clear by the fact that his wife became a member of Parliament from Gonda on a Hindu Mahasabha ticket, in 1952. In 1967, Nair himself won a Lok Sabha election from Bahraich on a ticket from the Bharatiya Jan Sangh, an offshoot of the RSS and the Mahasabha.

Dark Night notes:

The district magistrate of Faizabad was among the first to reach the spot once Abhiram Das finished the operation successfully in the dead of the night. At that time the masjid only had a handful of people and Ayodhya was asleep. No one would have known about the incident – or people would have come to know so late that no commotion would have been possible – had the district magistrate acted swiftly and removed the idol and images of Hindu deities from the mosque and scratched away the writings, not many in number, from its inner and outer walls. So, he could have easily restored the mosque’s status quo ante without

creating any fuss among Hindu believers. That was also expected of any district magistrate anywhere in the country ... the FIR of the incident was lodged only at nine in the morning though Nair had reached the spot at five. It took the district magistrate an hour and a half more to send a brief radio message to the premier of the United Provinces, Govind Ballabh Pant, as well as to the state's chief secretary and home secretary.

Akshay Brahmachari, the secretary of the Faizabad District Congress at the time, wrote in a memorandum to Lal Bahadur Shastri, the home minister of the United Provinces:

From that very morning loudspeakers started announcing the appearance of Bhagwan, exhorting all Hindus to come for darshan. Tension went on increasing. Notices and handbills continued to be distributed. Thousands of people started pouring in for darshan into the city in cars and public carriers sent out from Faizabad.

Contrast this what happened at the Kamal Maula mosque. Bhargava described the administration's response. "We all know the idol is in a museum in London. The idol that we found after entering the complex manifested itself just outside the temple. We lifted it and took it into the *garbhagriha*"—the sanctum sanctorum—he said. "When we come out a governmental conspiracy was enacted. When people started finding out about the idol, the ASI stated in writing that no such idol had been found. They also arrested one of our associates. The next day we spoke to the SP and asked, 'If there was no idol why had he been arrested?' Then we reached the home of our associate, and the police arrested us."

"Everyone knew this was done by the Mahasabha," Bhargava told us. "The people who had been leading the Bhojshala agitation had been ineffective. I cannot understand what the point of clanging bells and making noise is." He said he had been asked many times what the aim

of his act was, when the Ram temple at Ayodhya was already being constructed. “But that took five hundred years. Are we going to wait five hundred for each temple? We have drawn up a list of forty-two thousand such structures in the country. If we spent five hundred years on each, how many generations will pass before we achieve our aims?”

At a time when the Narendra Modi government is preparing to celebrate the successful culmination of the campaign by Hindutva organisations to gain control over the Babri Masjid complex, this saga could be a sign of what lies ahead. The escalation of the issue occurred shortly before a new BJP government was sworn-in in the state. The new chief minister, Mohan Yadav, is a trusty Sangh man, who has risen through its ranks to his current position—his first act as chief minister was a campaign to ban the open sale of meat and fish. These are clear signs of the BJP’s hardening position on such issues in the state. The pre-Yadav administration removed the idol from the complex. How the Yadav government chooses to respond to this issue will be the test of how dramatic this change of guard is.

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